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Assessing Phishing Email Detection For Organizational Culture Impact On Social Engineering Vulnerability

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ABSTRACT

Phishing remains one of the most prevalent cyber threats targeting the human element of security, emphasizing the need for organizations to go beyond technical detection systems and foster a culture that supports secure behavior. This study examines the relationship between phishing email detection and the role of organizational culture, particularly cybersecurity cultural hygiene, in influencing vulnerability to social engineering attacks. The main objective is to explore how consistent security practices, leadership modeling, incident reporting, and continuous awareness collectively defined as cybersecurity cultural hygiene affect employee's susceptibility to phishing attempts. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining qualitative assessments of organizational culture with experimental analysis of phishing detection rates. The findings reveal that organizations with strong cybersecurity cultural hygiene exhibit significantly lower vulnerability to phishing-based social engineering attacks, as employees demonstrate greater awareness and responsiveness to phishing threats. The study concludes that cybersecurity is not solely a technical issue but a behavioral one shaped by everyday cultural norms and practices within the workplace.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, social engineering, phishing and organizational culture.

INTRODUCTION

The culture of an organization has a significant impact on how its people behave and think. It includes the standards, attitudes, and beliefs that control how staff members communicate with one another as well as third parties (Georgiadou, Mouzakitis, Bounas, et al., 2022). Organizational culture affects how employees view security procedures and react to possible threats in terms of cybersecurity (Uchendu et al., 2021). Social engineering attacks, which rely on human weaknesses rather than technological vulnerabilities, are much less likely to succeed in an environment that places a high priority on security knowledge and alertness. On the other hand, a culture that overlooks security might expose an organization to these kinds of attacks (Georgiadou, et al., 2022).

Social engineering attacks primarily rely on influencing human psychology to obtain illegal access to sensitive information. These strategies include phishing, pretexting, and baiting. These attacks frequently succeed because they take advantage of established social norms like trust to authority or a desire to provide a helping hand (Wiley et al., 2020). In organizations where employees are not adequately trained to recognize and respond to these tactics, the risk of falling victim to social engineering is significantly

higher. Therefore, the organization's culture regarding security awareness and its commitment to employee training are critical factors in its vulnerability to these types of attacks (Da Veiga, et al., 2020) . The impact of organizational culture on vulnerability to social engineering is multifaceted. A culture that encourages open communication and collaboration, while generally positive, can inadvertently increase the risk of social engineering if it leads to lax security practices. For instance, in a culture where sharing information freely is encouraged without proper controls, employees may inadvertently disclose sensitive information to unauthorized individuals (Ahmad et al., 2020). Furthermore, employees may be more inclined to agree with fraudulent requests that seem to emanate from top management if the organization has a hierarchical culture that opposes questioning authority. Establishing a culture that maintains a balance between openness and collaboration and a strong emphasis on security is crucial for firms looking to reduce the danger of social engineering attacks (Alenezi et al., 2021). This demands an organizational shift such that security is seen as an essential component of the organization's core principles and day-to-day activities (Justine et al., 2024).

Davies (2021) highlighted that it is important to motivate staff members at all levels to actively participate in security maintenance, from adhering to best practices to reporting questionable activity. Organizations must also consider the role of leadership in driving cultural change to enhance security. Leaders set the tone for the organization's culture and are responsible for promoting a security-first mindset. When leaders prioritize cybersecurity and model secure behaviors, they influence the broader organizational culture, encouraging employees to follow suit. Programs for ongoing education and awareness should also be put in place to make sure staff members are prepared to see and react to social engineering techniques (Albladi & Weir et al., 2020). In conclusion, the vulnerability of an organization to social engineering attacks is closely linked to its culture. By fostering a culture that prioritizes security, organizations can significantly reduce their susceptibility to these attacks (AlGhamdi et al., 2020). This study seeks to explore the relationship between organizational culture and vulnerability to social engineering, identifying the specific cultural attributes that increase risk and recommending shifts that can enhance overall security (Uchendu et al., 2022).

Problem Statement

According to reports from ISACAs State of Cybersecurity, social engineering is the top cyberthreat for organizations from 2016 to 2022, Social engineering attacks were experienced by 85% of organizations in 2022, an increase of 16% over four years, the average annual cost of social engineering attacks for organizations in 2022 has exceeded \$1.4 million, an increase of 8% compared to the previous year (Uchendu et al., 2022), highlighting the significant role human factors play in organizational security vulnerabilities. Because organizational cultures remain potential weak points, many businesses are vulnerable to social engineering attacks even with advances in technology protection (Aldawood et al., 2019). These attacks frequently take advantage of the trust, practices, and communication styles that are established in the workplace, leading to major security breaches that could have been avoided with a more security-conscious culture (Debb & McClellan, 2021). This study addresses the urgent need to assess how phishing email detection on organizational culture, Impact social engineering vulnerability, identifying phishing indicators and evaluate the specific components that contribute to or mitigate the risk of phishing attacks.

Research Questions

The main questions addressed by this research are:

1. How does organizational culture influence employee's susceptibility to phishing emails?
2. What specific cultural factors (such as., trust, communication, risk awareness) are most strongly associated with social engineering vulnerability?
3. To what extent do employee's perceptions of organizational culture correlate with their ability to identify and respond to phishing attempts?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is Assessing Phishing Email Detection for Organizational Culture Impact on Social Engineering Vulnerability. The specific objectives are:

- i. Evaluate the relationship between organizational culture and employees' susceptibility to phishing emails.
- ii. Identify key cultural factors (such as., trust, communication, risk awareness) that contribute to social engineering vulnerability.
- iii. Assess employee's perceptions of organizational culture and their impact on phishing email recognition and response behaviors.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research Design: The study adopts a quantitative survey-based approach to assess the impact of organizational culture on employee's susceptibility to phishing emails. This design allows for a broad and systematic exploration of the relationship between organizational culture and social engineering vulnerability, providing actionable insights for organizations.

Population: The target population for this study comprises employees across various industries in Abuja Nigeria such as Guarantee Trust Bank, United bank of Africa Federal Inland Revenue Services, Aiben group and Ave Maria University who are potentially exposed to phishing emails in their workplace.

Sampling Technique: A stratified random sampling was employed, dividing the population into subgroups based on factors such as industry type, organization size, and job role. This technique ensures diversity and reduces bias in the sample. The sample size of the study was 200.

Data Collection Method: The researcher used questionnaire as the instrument for data collection.

Data Analysis: The data collected for this study were analyzed using Microsoft Excel, leveraging its built-in functions and tools to examine the relationship between organizational culture and phishing email susceptibility. Descriptive statistics, such as mean, median, mode, standard deviation, and frequency distributions, were calculated using Excel functions to summarize survey responses and provide an overview of participant's perceptions and behaviors. For inferential analysis, Excel's Data Analysis Toolpak was used to perform correlation analysis and regression analysis to identify significant relationships between cultural factors (such as., trust, communication, risk awareness) and phishing susceptibility. Pivot tables were employed to organize and summarize large datasets, while charts and graphs (such as., bar charts, scatter plots) visually represent trends and patterns.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In a study carried out by Pollini et al., (2022) presents a holistic/Human Factors (HF) approach, where the individual, organizational and technological factors are investigated in pilot healthcare organizations to show how HF vulnerabilities may impact on cybersecurity risks. An overview of current challenges in relation to cybersecurity is first provided, followed by the presentation of an integrated top-down and bottom-up methodology using qualitative and quantitative research methods to assess the level of maturity of the pilot organizations with respect to their capability to face and tackle cyber threats and attacks (Willie, 2023, Kannelonning & Katsikas, 2023). This approach adopts a user-centered perspective, involving both the organizations management and employees, The results show that a better cybersecurity culture does not always correspond with more rule compliant behavior. In addition, conflicts among cybersecurity rules and procedures may trigger human vulnerabilities (Daengsi et al.). In conclusion, the integration of traditional technical solutions with guidelines to enhance CIS systems by leveraging HF in cybersecurity may lead to the adoption of non-technical countermeasures (such as user awareness) for a comprehensive and holistic way to manage cyber security in organizations. The limitation of the study is that the proposed approach cannot be generalized to other types of organizations in different domains. Kolluri, (2019) presents a review on a revolutionary technology often referred to as "The AI Sentry, 'This is an advanced technological strategy to combat social engineering attacks through artificial intelligence (AI).

Siddiqi et al., (2022) highlighted that as cybersecurity strategies become more robust and challenging, cybercriminals are mutating cyberattacks to be more evasive. Recent studies have highlighted the use of social engineering by criminals to exploit the human factor in an organization’s security architecture. Social engineering attacks exploit specific human attributes and psychology to bypass technical security measures for malicious acts. Social engineering is becoming a pervasive approach used for compromising individuals and organizations (is relatively more convenient to compromise a human compared to discovering a vulnerability in the security system). To counter such attacks, a better understanding of the attack tactics is highly essential. Hence, their paper provides an in-depth analysis of the approaches used to conduct social engineering-based cyberattacks (Yasin, 2021). This study discusses human vulnerabilities employed by criminals in recent security breaches. Further, the paper highlights the existing approaches, including machine learning-based methods, to counter social engineering-based cyberattacks. The limitation of the study is that there is no systematic flow of steps to follow in case of a SE-based cyberattack or threat. Montañez et al., (2020) presented a framework for systematizing human cognition through the lens of social engineering cyberattacks, which exploit weaknesses in human’s cognition functions. The framework is extended from the standard cognitive psychology to accommodate components that emerge from the cyber security context (Lin et al., 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of Respondents

This section provides an overview of the respondent's demographic characteristics, including their organizational type, sector of operation, position, and years of experience. Key statistics such as percentages and frequencies are presented in tables and charts for clarity.

Table I: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table II: Sex/Age range of Respondents

Category	Frequency			Percentage
Government	45			22.5%
Private sector	100			50.0%
Academic research	30			15.0%
Others	25			15%
Sex	18-30	31-50	51-60	
Male	45	52	7	
Female	53	25	18	

Table III: Primary sector of Respondents

Primary Sector		
Cybersecurity	40	20.0%
Information Technology	60	30.0%
Finance	35	17.5%
Healthcare	25	12.5%
Others	40	20%

Table IV: Respondents Position in Organization

Position in organization		
Senior Management	30	15.0%
IT/Cybersecurity Staff	70	35.0%
Human Resources	40	20.0%
General Employee	50	25.0%
Others	10	5.0%

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic data collected from the survey. Frequencies (counts) and percentages were calculated for each category, such as organization type, sector of operation, and employee position. The percentage for each category was derived using the formula: $\text{Percentage} = (\text{Frequency of Category} / \text{Total Number of Respondents}) \times 100$

In the Type of Organization category:

Government: 45 respondents out of 200

Percentage = $(45/200) \times 100 = 22.5\%$

Private Sector: 100 respondents out of 200

Percentage = $(100/200) \times 100 = 50.0\%$

These calculations were repeated for all demographic categories to provide a clear summary of the respondent's profiles.

Fig. I: A bar chart showing the distribution of respondents by organization type.

Awareness of Phishing and Social Engineering

This section analyzes respondent's awareness of phishing emails and social engineering attacks. It includes data on how employees stay informed about these threats and their self-rated ability to identify phishing attempts.

Key Findings

85% of respondents are aware of phishing emails and social engineering attacks.

The most common sources of information are:

- iv. Internal training - 60%

- v. Industry reports 40%
- vi. Conferences/workshops 25%

70% of respondents rated their ability to identify phishing emails as "High" or "Very High."

Descriptive Technique

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize awareness levels and sources of information about phishing threats. Percentages were calculated for each response category using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage} = \left(\frac{\text{Frequency of Response}}{\text{Total Number of Respondents}} \right) \times 100$$

Awareness of Phishing Emails

Yes: 170 respondents out of 200
 Percentage = $(170/200) \times 100 = 85\%$
 No: 30 respondents out of 200
 Percentage = $(30/200) \times 100 = 15\%$

Sources of Information

Internal Training: 120 respondents out of 200
 Percentage = $(120/200) \times 100 = 60\%$
 Industry Reports: 80 respondents out of 200
 Percentage = $(80/200) \times 100 = 40\%$

These calculations were repeated for all response categories to summarize the data effectively.

Sources of Information on Phishing Threats

Fig. II: A bar chart showing the percentage of respondents who use each source of information.

Organizational Culture and Phishing Susceptibility: This section explores the relationship between organizational culture and employees' susceptibility to phishing emails. It includes data on trust levels, communication effectiveness, and the frequency of phishing simulation exercises.

Key Findings

65% of respondents described the level of trust within their organization as "High" or "Very High."
 55% of respondents believe communication about cybersecurity risks is "Effective" or "Very Effective."
 40% of organizations conduct phishing simulation exercises quarterly, while 30% conduct them annually.
 Analysis of trust levels, communication effectiveness, and simulation frequency.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize trust levels, communication effectiveness, and simulation frequency. Percentages were calculated for categorical responses, while means were calculated for numerical or Likert-scale responses.

Percentages

For categorical responses (such as., trust levels), percentages were calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage} = \left(\frac{\text{Frequency of Response}}{\text{Total Number of Respondents}} \right) \times 100\% = \left(\frac{\text{Total No. of Respondents}}{\text{Frequency of Response}} \right) \times 100$$

High Trust Level: 130 respondents out of 200

$$\text{Percentage} = \left(\frac{130}{200} \right) \times 100 = 65\%$$

Means

For Likert-scale responses (such as., communication effectiveness rated from 1 to 5), the mean was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\sum \text{Responses}}{\text{Total Number of Respondents}} \quad \text{Mean} = \frac{\text{Total Number of Responses}}{\text{Total Number of Respondents}}$$

Communication effectiveness ratings: 4, 5, 3, 4, 5 (for 5 respondents)

$$\text{Mean} = 4 + 5 + 3 + 4 + 5 = 21$$

$$\text{Mean} = 21 / 5 = 4.2$$

These calculations were repeated for all relevant categories to summarize the data effectively.

Frequency of Phishing Simulation Exercises

Fig. III: A bar chart showing the frequency of phishing simulation exercises in organizations.

Impact of Organizational Culture on Phishing Susceptibility: This section examines how organizational culture influences employee's ability to handle phishing emails. It includes data on the impact of culture on awareness, reporting, and collaboration.

Key Findings

75% of respondents reported that organizational culture has "Increased Awareness" of phishing threats. 60% of respondents agreed that their organization's culture encourages proactive cybersecurity practices. 50% of organizations have seen measurable improvements in reducing phishing susceptibility, such as:

- xii. Improved threat detection - 40%
- xiii. Enhanced incident response - 35%

Correlation analysis to explore relationship between cultural factors

Percentages were calculated to summarize the impact of organizational culture. Correlation analysis was used to explore the relationship between cultural factors (such as., trust, communication) and phishing susceptibility.

Percentages were calculated to summarize the impact of organizational culture on phishing susceptibility. The formula used was:

$$\text{Percentage} = \left(\frac{\text{Frequency of Response}}{\text{Total Number of Respondents}} \right) \times 100$$

Increased Awareness: 150 respondents out of 200

$$\text{Percentage} = \left(\frac{150}{200} \right) \times 100 = 75\%$$

Improved Reporting: 100 respondents out of 200

$$\text{Percentage} = \left(\frac{100}{200} \right) \times 100 = 50\%$$

Inferential Statistics: Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was used to explore the relationship between cultural factors (e.g., trust, communication) and phishing susceptibility. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was calculated using Excel's CORREL function:

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Data for Trust Levels (x) and Phishing Susceptibility Scores (y) divided in two columns.

Using the formula =CORREL (range_x, range_y) to calculate the correlation coefficient.

Trust Levels (x): 4, 5, 3, 4, 5

Phishing Susceptibility (y): 2, 1, 3, 2, 1

Correlation Coefficient (r):

$$r = \text{CORREL}(x, y) = -0.79$$

A negative value indicates an inverse relationship: higher trust levels correlate with lower phishing susceptibility.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study reveal a significant relationship between organizational culture and employee's susceptibility to phishing emails, highlighting the critical role of cultural factors such as trust, communication, and risk awareness in shaping cybersecurity behaviors. Respondents indicated that organizations with a strong culture of security awareness, regular training, and open communication were better equipped to identify and respond to phishing threats. However, challenges such as lack of employee awareness, insufficient training programs, and limited budgets for cybersecurity were identified as key barriers to effective phishing prevention. The correlation analysis further supported these findings, showing that higher levels of trust and effective communication within organizations were associated with lower phishing susceptibility. These results underscore the importance of fostering a proactive cybersecurity culture, investing in employee education, and implementing clear threat intelligence frameworks. By addressing these challenges and adopting the recommended strategies, organizations can significantly reduce their vulnerability to social engineering attacks and enhance their overall cybersecurity resilience.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that organizational culture plays a pivotal role in shaping employees' susceptibility to phishing emails and social engineering attacks. A culture that prioritizes trust, open communication, and continuous learning significantly enhances employees' ability to identify and respond to phishing threats. Conversely, a lack of awareness, inadequate training, and resistance to change exacerbate vulnerability. The correlation analysis further validated that cultural factor such as trust and communication effectiveness are inversely related to phishing susceptibility, emphasizing the need for organizations to address these cultural dimensions. These findings highlight the human and cultural aspects of cybersecurity, demonstrating that technical measures alone are insufficient to combat social engineering threats. Organizations must adopt a holistic approach that integrates cultural, behavioral, and technical strategies to build resilience against phishing and other cyber threats.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to help organizations reduce phishing susceptibility and strengthen their cybersecurity posture:

- v. Enhance Employee Awareness: Conduct regular phishing awareness campaigns and workshops to educate employees about the latest threats and attack techniques.
- vi. Implement Comprehensive Training Programs: Provide ongoing, role-specific training that covers phishing identification, reporting procedures, and cybersecurity best practices.
- vii. Invest in Cybersecurity Resources: Allocate adequate budgets for advanced threat detection tools, skilled personnel, and employee training.
- viii. Conduct Regular Phishing Simulations: Use simulation exercises to test employees' readiness and identify areas for improvement.
- ix. Develop Clear Threat Intelligence Frameworks: Standardize processes for collecting, analyzing, and acting on threat intelligence, such as Indicators of Compromise (IoCs). By implementing these recommendations, organizations can build a robust cybersecurity culture, reduce susceptibility to phishing attacks, and enhance their overall resilience against evolving cyber threats.

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